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RIGOUROUS -
secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

Deliverable 6.2

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

Title	Dissemination and Communication Plan
Document description	The deliverable reports the complete plan of activities towards dissemination, and impact assessment to be carried during the project duration, as part of Task 6.1
Nature	Public
Task	T6.1
Status	Final
WP	WP6
Lead Partner	ITAV
Partners Involved	ALL
Date	30/06/2023

Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 01	Lenovo	20/06/2023	Text to Clause 6.2.3 - Standardization Dissemination was added.
Version 02	ITAV	29/30/2023	Integration of final contributions
Final Version	UMU	30/06/2023	Final edition

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main contributions of this document are:

- Presentation of the communication, dissemination, and standardization plan;
- Presentation of the early achievements according to this plan.

This document includes communication and dissemination plans and related activities. Communication includes all the activities related to the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's community. This includes explaining its research in a way that is understandable for the non-specialist, e.g., the media and the public. Dissemination includes activities related to raising awareness of its results in a technical community working in the same research field. In general, this will be done through publications, standardization and participation, and organization of technical events.

The communication and dissemination plan started at the proposal stage with the identification of the various components of the project that could have an impact on the research point of view. After that, and from project start, it is structured in various phases. At the initial stages of the project, the focus is on communication (e.g., setting up the web portal and social media accounts and high-level project presentations) to make the project known not just to the technical community but to a larger audience outside the project topics, including the public (e.g. student community and technology users). Dissemination activities also start in this early phase with preliminary technical ideas and further complemented by standardization efforts which includes primary contributions to different SDOs.

In accordance with the plan, some early results have already been produced. Some highlights follow:

- Communication
 - Design of promotion material, website, and creation of news, and social media accounts, along with initial actions to raise awareness about the project through these means. This already resulted in several website visits and a high number of relevant followers.
 - Communication talks and events participations
- Dissemination
 - Two accepted publications
 - Dissemination talks
- Standardization
 - Two study items in 3GPP SA3 work group
 - One group report in ETSI PDL work group

2 INTRODUCTION

Communication and dissemination are two of the critical activities for the RIGOUROUS project:

- **Communication:** It includes all the activities related to the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's community. This includes communication of its research in a way that it is understood by non-specialists, e.g., the media and the public.
- **Dissemination:** It includes activities related to raising awareness of its results in a technical community working in the same research field. In general, this will be done through peer-reviewed publications in academic conferences and journals and participation and organization of technical events.

These activities combine complementary actions that, altogether, provide an intentional and effective relay of information and awareness towards the whole array of relevant target audiences (e.g., cloud computing industry, the standardization development bodies (SDOs), the research community, decision-makers (governments, public agencies, umbrella organizations, and regulatory organizations), end-user communities and the general public. This audience also comprises a broad group of stakeholders, including policymakers, citizens, and public authorities, that could benefit from new 6G services and enhanced 6G security. These target stakeholders are crucial to having a long-lasting and highly beneficial societal impact on EU citizens' daily activities and lives. It is of utmost importance for the success of future commercial implementations to properly communicate to our target audience what suite of brand-new 6G technologies fits the most for the specific business and technology drivers in every single of the selected applications.

By introducing our innovative communication and communication protocols, we plan to become a broadband for disseminating information of interest regarding 6G usage to the European industry to compete in global markets successfully. It is essential to create a communication scheme that will reflect the diversity and, at the same time, will assist external stakeholders and the general public to understand the journey of each undertaken application as they progress through the project's roadmap.

The goal of the proposal stage was to lay down the foundations for all activities following in the project execution phases both in technical and legal terms. The communication and dissemination plan is included during the project execution phase. All activities will be carried out in parallel, but the emphasis of each of them will be different depending on the phase of the project. At the initial stages of the project, the focus is on communication (e.g., setting up the web and social media and high-level project presentations) to make the project known not just to the R&D community but to a larger audience outside the project, including the public. Dissemination activities also start in this phase with preliminary technical contributions. More specifically, all the activities below are initiated in this phase:

- Web portal and social media accounts
- Project brochure
- High-level project presentation and participation at events to explain project scope.
- Participation in events for a general audience (e.g., open science week).

The above activities are allocated more effort at the beginning of the project due to the preparation of the initial communication resources and framework needed throughout the project, but they continue until the end of the project and after the project ends.

During the presentation of the results phase, dissemination activities have more intensity. More specifically, these activities include:

- Publication of research results in technical journals and conferences.
- Enrolment of PhD and Master students on the topics of the project.
- Participation in public exhibitions and demonstrations.
- Organization of special events (e.g., technical workshops).

The project's communication, dissemination and standardization plan in this document is based on a coherent framework. However, it will be periodically updated throughout the project if, for instance, new activities need to be defined or new collaboration and dissemination opportunities appear. It will be treated as a living document, which will be reviewed and adapted regularly during the project. In other words, undertaken communication actions will be consistent, and, at the same time, they will comprehend a portfolio of information that are of interest to each target group. The following sections describe in detail the work plan for each activity. Furthermore, the early achievements in some of the activities are also listed.

3 COMMUNICATION PLAN

3.1. Work Plan

All actions contributing to the diffusion of the project's results beyond the Consortium and the direct stakeholders are considered Communication activities. The main objective is to maximize the project's innovation potential and attract a wide range of stakeholders who are invited to embrace the project's results and benefit from the project's advancements. In this direction, the project will:

- Define concrete and measurable objectives for the communication activities and link these objectives with the appropriate target groups.
- Implement a solid, modern, and inclusive communication strategy, accompanied by a realistic plan to reach these objectives.
- Set up the different channels, tools, and mechanisms that will be used to implement the communication plan and reach the targeted audiences.
- Define the guidelines for implementing communication actions (e.g., project identity, messages to convey, internal reporting rules, etc.).
- Put into action an iterative communication and learning process, which shall measure the level of response per communication mechanism and interpret the corresponding insights.
- Closely monitor the impact of the communication activities to apply corrective actions whenever necessary and identify opportunities that can maximize visibility.

The communication strategy is driven by the following communication objectives, which are directly linked with the different phases of the project and the corresponding targeted audiences (Table 1).

Table 1 Communication Phases and Objectives

Phase	Objectives
Phase A	O1: To create awareness of the project among the full range of the general public's stakeholders. O2: To provide a clear view of the project's concept, goals, and results by formulating adapted key messages and preparing communication material.
Phase B	O3: To create an active community of the general public's stakeholders and collect feedback to be taken into account by the project's activities. O4: To support targeted communication of the project's results.
Phase C	O5: To prepare the ground for exploiting the project's results.

The following activities are planned:

- **Public website:** WP6 will create a comprehensive public website containing all relevant information about the project. It will provide centralized access to the various publicly available deliverables, publications, and articles related to the project. The site will be regularly updated over the project's lifetime with project publications and publicity materials, such as flyers, posters, public deliverables, organized workshops, available services, etc.
- **Social networking:** The project intends to develop its presence on social networks and media. These channels will be used for interaction with the more professional community (researchers, SMEs, large industry) and with the general public (while being cautious with personal data protection issues). The participation of members of the Consortium in public events, key achievements, publications, and software releases will be announced in established social network communities such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and ResearchGate.
- **Promotional material:** The project will prepare appropriate printed materials to promote the project outcomes to the general public and the graphic identity for the project, supporting the other dissemination activities of RIGOUROUS. Additionally, the Consortium will produce press releases to publicize the progress of the project and other promotional materials about the RIGOUROUS main goals and achievements (e.g., flyers, fact sheets, roll-ups, videos, electronic posters, quarterly newsletters, and other printed material).
- **Participation in third-party events (research/academic, industry, others):** the RIGOUROUS consortium will strive to include the project's presence in third-party events relevant to the scope of RIGOUROUS, including the participation in scientific conferences and workshops, seminars, innovation events, tradeshow, exhibitions, organization of special sessions at reference conferences and workshops, demonstrations and any other relevant activities that prospectively lead to the involvement of a diversified spectrum of audiences from different backgrounds, as a way to foster the visibility and the impact of the project and its research topics.
- **Organization of local workshops:** RIGOUROUS will organize local workshops, co-located with the project's plenary meetings, held in different countries (at least one local workshop for each EU Country represented in the Consortium). The goal is to organize one-day local workshops to which relevant stakeholders will be invited. Each of these workshops will provide an overview of RIGOUROUS and highlight innovations, including short presentations from invited stakeholders and related research projects. This approach is a cost-effective way of increasing the impact and dissemination of the project. Moreover, workshops will be conducted within the four Use Cases, further amplifying the local impact and engaging the respective communities.
- **Organization of international seminars:** three international seminars will be organized, inviting research, industry, and end-user stakeholders in joint sessions of discussion over the developments of RIGOUROUS. Each of these seminars will be aligned with a different

phase of the project: the kick-off seminar will focus on analyzing the state-of-art, connecting to relevant ongoing projects, collecting the requirements from different stakeholders, and discussing the RIGOUROUS concept and preliminary architecture. The mid-term seminar will focus on the technical and research advancements introduced while developing the RIGOUROUS components and on influencing other projects, decision-makers, and SDOs. The final seminar will focus on showcasing the integrated RIGOUROUS framework and disseminating the findings of the project evaluation phase, further influencing the industry and preparing post-project exploitation activities.

- **Publications:** RIGOUROUS outcomes will be disseminated through publications in international scientific conferences, journals, and magazines. Even though an extended list of relevant scientific publications will be developed in the scope of the dissemination plan, preliminary targets have already been identified. Other publications, such as newspapers, bulletins, or newsletters, will capture the attention of a wider audience.
- **Open-source contributions:** RIGOUROUS will contribute to the open-source community, both in the form of contributions to the already existing open-source projects to be used in the project and through making publicly available complete software components developed within the project.
- **Advanced training:** RIGOUROUS will support advanced training activities, providing support for M.Sc. and Ph.D. research thesis directly related to the project topics and promoting the hands-on use of the RIGOUROUS concept and tools in specialized training courses provided by the academic and public research institutions involved (with the support of the other members of RIGOUROUS consortium), such as master courses and shorter advanced training courses specifically tailored for IT professionals.
- **Collaboration with other H2020 projects, dissemination mechanisms, and community building:** Another essential aspect of our overall communication actions and protocols is the establishment of collaboration and liaison activities with interested or interesting initiatives. RIGOUROUS will set up a smooth and direct liaison mechanism with major ongoing projects partners are involved and strive to have active participation in the dissemination and liaising activities conducted by other concertation actions in related technologies such as 6G, AI/ML, etc.

4 DISSEMINATION PLAN

4.1. Dissemination Work

Table 2 summarizes the planned activities organized in three phases and a subset of the related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). For the sake of conciseness, activity-specific KPIs were left

outside this table (e.g., quality and impact indicators for the scientific publications, cohesion indicators measuring joint papers, and quality indicators related to the visits to the website), even though they will be addressed during project implementation. During the project, this dissemination plan will be refined, continuously monitored, evaluated in terms of its implementation, and systematically updated accordingly.

Table 2 RIGUROUS dissemination plan

Activity	Phase I (Year 1)	Phase 2 (Year 2)	Phase 3 (Year 3 and Beyond)	Target KPIs (Year 1 to Year 3)
Website	Established in Month 3	Ongoing activity (content updates)	Ongoing activity (content updates)	Monthly visitors: 200/350/500
Social Media	Established in Month 3	Ongoing activity (content updates)	Ongoing activity (content updates)	Number of followers: 200/300/400
Promotional Materials	Since Month 3: graphic identity, templates, whitepaper, factsheet, newsletters	Ongoing: update of materials, new materials reflecting ongoing work, newsletters	Ongoing: update of materials, new materials reflecting ongoing work, newsletters	Quarterly newsletters (4 per year)
Participation in Conferences and other third-party events	Participation in events, presentation of the project's approach, collection of feedback	Presentation of project results, demos, and dissemination of project results in partners' events	Presentation of mature results, business cases, business models, and policy contributions	Research events >= 6/6/9 (Y1/Y2/Y3) Industry events >= 2/4/4 Demos >= 0/2/4
Org. of local workshops and int. seminars	Kick-off seminar + 2 local workshops	Mid-term seminar + 4 local workshops	Final seminar + 1 local workshop + 4 pilot workshops	Total number of participants in these events > 500
Publications	Initial publications, position papers, white papers, preliminary research results	Publication of tools, first results, and preliminary evaluation	Publish time-tested and mature results - target top-tier conferences and venues	Research papers: 6/9/12 (Y1-Y2-Y3). Other publications: 6/4/6 (Y1-Y2-Y3)
Open-source repositories	Identification of relevant open-	Initial contributions;	Contribution of complete	Contributions to ongoing projects:

	source projects	creation of a community	systems, integrators; demos follow up with the users of the community	>= 4 Contributions of complete systems: >= 2
Advanced Training	Identification of potential M.Sc. and Ph.D. dissertation topics aligned with RIGOUROUS. Engaging of candidates.	1st round of completed MSc dissertations. Engagement of additional candidates. Preliminary training materials.	MSc and PhD dissertations. Training materials integrated into advanced training programs (master courses, industry)	Concluded thesis: MSc's up to Y3 >= 9 PhDs up to Y3 >=3 Impacted training programs: >= 3
Collaboration with other H2020 projects, dissemination mechanisms, and community building	Identification of relevant projects; contacts via existing links and CSA activities. Form first connections, capitalize previous communications and links that may exist from past projects and activities	Participation in events; presentation of results; Key stakeholders, participation in events	Demos; collaborations; formation of new consortia	Reached projects, mechanisms, and communities >= 4 (Y1) 6 (Y2) 9 (Y3)
Standardization effort	Project research topic related contribution identification and presentation to related SDO(s)	Ongoing activity (content updates)	Ongoing activity (content updates)	Agreed Contributions to group report, study items or a work item. Minimum of 2 contribution per year.

Table 3 identifies the research conferences, scientific journals, and industry events as primary candidates for RIGOUROUS dissemination actions. They were selected due to their scope, reputation, and relevance to the scientific and industrial communities.

Table 3 Target research conferences, workshops, journals, and industry events

Research Conferences and Workshops
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Conference on Research in Computer Security • IEEE Secure Development Conference • IEEE Int. Conf. on Trust, Security, and Privacy in Computing and Communications • IEEE Symposium on Security & Privacy • Network and Distributed System Security Symposium • IEEE Global Communications Conference • IEEE Trans. On Mobile Computing • IEEE Trans. On Communications • ACM SIGCOMM • IEEE Int. Workshop on Information Forensics and Security • IEEE Int. Conf. on Availability, Reliability & Security • IFIP TC 11 Int. Conf. on ICT Systems Security and Privacy Protection • IEEE Int. Conf. on Network Softwarization • IFIP/IEEE Int. Symposium on Integrated Network Management • Int. Conf. on Communications • IEEE Trans. On Multimedia
Scientific Journals
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACM Trans. On Inf. & System Security • IEEE Trans. On Net. And Service Management • Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence • Computers & Security, Elsevier • IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications • IEEE Internet of Things • Security and Communication Networks • IEEE Security & Privacy • IEEE Trans. On Information Foresincs and Security • IEEE Trans. On Dependable and Secure Computing • IEEE Communication Magazine • IEEE Communications Standards Magazine • IEEE Network
Industry Events
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AR & VR World Summit • EuCNC • 6G Summit • SANS Security (various regional editions) • Cyber Security Expo • Standards Organization Participation

Communication aspects will be considered throughout all the project stages to ensure a proper strategic alignment between the various communication activities, overall project goals, and impact amplification. A communication campaign will be carried out to ensure proper diffusion of the outcomes of RIGOUROUS towards the public in general. Table 4 presents the communication target groups for each activity type (darker bullets represent primary targets; light bullets represent secondary targets). The general communication flow relies on the relational networks established through the dissemination activities as a primary channel for amplifying RIGOUROUS impacts.

Table 4 Communication target groups per activity type

Activity type	Vendors	Technology Providers	Industry	Scientific community	Decision makers and regulators	End users	Public at large
Website	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Social Media	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Promotional Materials	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Participation in scientific conferences & workshops	●	○	○	●	○		
Participation in industry events	●	●	●	○	○		
Local RIGOUROUS workshops	●	●	●	○	●	●	○
International RIGOUROUS seminars	●	●	●	○	●	●	○
Collaboration with other H2020 projects	●	●	○	●	○	○	
EC Dissemination Mechanisms	●	●	●	●	●	○	○
Scientific Publications	○	○	○	●	○		
Publications in general media	○	○	○	○	○	●	●
Open-source repositories	○	●	●	●	○		
Advanced Training	●	●	●	●	●		
Community building	●	●	●	●	●	○	○

Apart from centralized project dissemination activities, each partner has complemented individual plans to disseminate project results and achievements in diverse channels, depending on their expertise, aiming to raise public awareness and respective National and European stakeholders. Table 5 outlines those plans.

Table 5 RIGOUROUS partner's individual dissemination plans

Partner	Individual Dissemination Plan
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UMU	<p>UMU will exploit different communication channels to maximize its outreach to different audiences. The main target groups are: End users, Business ecosystem partners, Investors, General Public, Public administration, policymakers, System developers, the Research community, and International forums. The main dissemination activities will be scientific publications in international peer-reviewed scientific journals, magazines, book chapters, and conferences. The editorship of books and chapters related to the project research items will also be exploited to externalize RIGOUROUS work and document the advances regarding state-of-the-art achievements. Contributions and participation in international conferences, workshops, and summits are also envisaged, as well as contributions to relevant international Fora and Coordination Actions.</p>
ORO	<p>ORO dissemination target groups are: Romanian Technical Universities students, assistants and professors, end-users from the business sector and public sector, SMEs, and high-tech entrepreneurs. Moreover, ORO will disseminate the project result to Orange Corporate and Orange affiliates. ORO will promote the project's value, benefits, and technical enablers in the high-tech conferences and workshops, including IEEE Communications conferences held in Bucharest. ORO is actively involved in organizing DefCamp, one of East Europe's most important cyber security conferences. In this context, we can bring in front of the audience the results from the project pilots stressing the benefits of using the developed platform and tech enablers. During public events such as Smart City caravans, where both business and public authorities are attending, we will have the opportunity to present the outcome of our research and to collect feedback and additional proposal that we may consider for fine-tuning the use cases and the architecture.</p>
LNVO	<p>Lenovo plans to perform dissemination through publications in international scientific conferences, journals, and magazines. Further, the dissemination will include active contributions and presentations to one or more of: the international standardization bodies like ETSI, 3GPP, 6G-IA, or NGMN are envisioned to communicate the project activities. In addition, Lenovo will also support disseminating new security concepts, schemes, and tools that the project will develop through common project activities such as joint workshops, webinars, and project blog posts.</p>
RHEA	<p>RHEA will exploit the security risk assessment of the RIGOUROUS concept by verifying the security resilience of the proposed 6G platform. Then, the objective is to propose a plan of "how to promote security resilience" into the proposed platform. RIGOUROUS exploitable assets will also be demonstrated at exhibitions and international relevant events so that RHEA plans to perform dissemination through the publication of the R&D results in peer-reviewed papers, conference proceedings, white papers, and the selected appropriate journal papers. The innovative features of the expected RIGOUROUS findings also help to design and promote new business models. RHEA will collaborate with other EU market players by considering a customer channel by targeting the audience of potential customers from governments and commercials,</p>

	organizing meetings with key stakeholders from industry and potential investors, and presenting RIGOUROUS obtained results.
EBOS	EBOS, in close collaboration with all consortium partners, will amplify the communication and dissemination efforts of the RIGOUROUS project through existing and new channels with stakeholders and end-users. Communication and dissemination activities about the project activities, its achievements, and expected technological results will be initiated by EBOS early in the project, thereby raising awareness about RIGOUROUS existence to meet the desired engagement level by the end of the project. EBOS will promote the use of the project's technical solutions towards European ICT SMEs to enable and encourage them to use the project's exploitable assets and services. The company plans to participate in at least two industrial exhibitions and/or conferences per year, promoting the project while liaising in parallel with relevant European Technology Platforms (NESSI, NEM, NGI, NetWorld 2020, Vision2020, CARIE, etc.) and other relevant European bodies and initiatives. Furthermore, it will also contribute to more traditional dissemination means (flyers, posters, high-impact public website posts, press releases, white papers, participation, and presentation to scientific/professional conferences and other related networking events). In addition, EBOS is currently serving as the Dissemination and Communication Manager in 4 ongoing H2020 projects (DARLENE, SANCUS, COPA EUROPE, 5G- ERA) and will therefore use its experience and knowledge towards a more effective dissemination strategy, also for the RIGOUROUS project.
WINGS	WINGS will participate in EUCNC and one leading IEEE or ACM conference (during the lifetime of the project). It will also contribute to one magazine or journal publication per year. WINGS will also participate in activities within 6G-IA, ECSO, and BDVA-DAIRO. It will also target one national conference per year on 5G or security and participation in one commercial fare.
ONE	ONE plans to disseminate the project's results in journals and scientific venues. Preference will go to joint papers, reflecting collaboration with other project partners on security and privacy, AI/ML, and AR/VR. Moreover, ONE also plans to support the Consortium in disseminating and demonstrating the project concepts and results in industry events such as SANS Security and other venues of interest. ONE also plans to leverage the project's outcomes to increase visibility and outreach to new segments of potential customers for its consultancy services in security, infrastructure management, and software integration.
ICT-FI	ICT-FI targets the publications of project outcomes in selected and high-impact journals and magazines on communications/networking (e.g., IEEE Communication Magazine, IEEE JSAC, IEEE Network, IEEE Internet of Things), and reputed international conferences (e.g., Globecom, ICC, WCNC, Infocom, EuCNC), as well as vertical-oriented publications (e.g., IEEE Trans. On Multimedia, IEEE Trans. on Mobile Computing, IEEE Trans. on Communications, IEEE Trans. On Cloud Computing), and that is in close collaboration with academic partners, such as the University of Oulu. ICT-FI will also

	disseminate the project findings among its partners (e.g., Nokia, Ericsson Finland, INFINERA, NEC, and other SMEs).
OULU	Besides disseminating the results of the research carried out in the project through scientific publications in high-impact conferences and journals and reflecting the project results in the courses of OULU, OULU will exploit the results to improve its 5G Test Network and make it more secure. OULU will leverage the 6G Flagship program to implement some technology transfer strategies where possible. The OULU team will also disseminate the work of the project among the different industrial partners of the 6G Flagship ecosystem. Whenever possible, OULU will also contribute the project's standards-relevant findings in scientific publications format to the IEEE Communications Standards Magazine and the IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (IEEE-CSCN), founded by OULU key personnel.
UWS	As a university, UWS will focus on making a significant contribution to new knowledge in the scientific/academic communities through high-quality, peer-reviewed publications in leading international journals, magazines (e.g., IEEE Transactions on Services Computing, Cloud Computing, Mobile Computing, etc.; IEEE Communications Magazines, Wireless Communications, etc.) and conferences (e.g., IEEE ICC, Globecom, WCNC, ICCE, etc.). The UWS team has an excellent track record in publications and has won several Best Paper Awards at recent international conferences. Moreover, pilot project demos will be exhibited and promoted in national and international venues (e.g., Glasgow Science Fair and the demo track of conferences) and through the participation in various open days and technical events organized by UWS, UK, European and international stakeholders such as UK Research Councils, IEEE, IET, KTN (Knowledge Transfer Network), InnovateUK, SICSA (Scottish Informatics and Computer Science Alliance) and the Royal Society as well as in standardization bodies. Apart from promoting the research conducted, these events will also enable the engagement of new beneficiaries and the creation of new educational and industrial links.
ITAV	ITAV expects to publish high-impact research works at international, high-quality peer-reviewed conferences proceedings (e.g., IEEE ICC, Globecom, WCNC, ICCE, etc.) and journals (IEEE Transactions on Services Computing, Cloud Computing, Mobile Computing, etc.; IEEE Communications Magazines, Wireless Communications, IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials), participate in the organization of conferences and workshops that have a discussion forum for cyber-resilience and cybersecurity or devoted to communications but where discussion the security of said infrastructures is relevant. ITAV hosts an extensive computation infrastructure, including a commercial-grade 5G deployment. This infrastructure allows the dissemination of the project results towards the realization of demonstration pilots, aiming at verticals for key players, or towards designing and evaluating disruptive, novel technologies and concepts. ITAV constantly promotes research and hosts students performing their master's and Ph.D. studies. RIGOUROURS will provide the underlying context for the development of relevant works, and the outcomes can be disseminated through

	lectures, participation in workshops, papers, and theses. Finally, ITAV is present in standardization activities such as 5G-PPP and will use these groups to disseminate the RIGOUROUS outcomes.
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4.2. Synergies with other Projects

The collaboration with other project has been focalized up to now in two main areas:

- Participation in the 6G-IA meetings and specially the SNS JU Phase 1 projects Webinars where all projects in the same strands present their work 23/02/2023; and the participation in the standardization workshop. Participation in the ETSI/SNS standardization event in Sophia Antipolis in February 2023.
- Organization of several workshops with other 5G projects, like the supporting of our project of the 5th International Workshop on Cyber-Security in Software-defined and Virtualized Infrastructures (SecSoft), 19 June 2023 // Madrid, Spain, or the proposal of a Workshop on Beyond actual 5G Architectures for 6G Services. for the IEEE Future Networks World Forum | 13-15 November 2023 // Baltimore, MD, USA

During next months it is expected a more extensive collaboration with project once identified the main architecture components and assets to contribute.

5 STANDARDIZATION PLAN

Besides the joint exploitation project, each RIGOUROUS partner will refine and implement an individual exploitation plan according to its profile and expectations from the project. Table 6 summarizes those plans.

Table 6 Partner Individual Exploitation Plan w.r.t. Standardization

Partner	Individual Exploitation Plans
UMU	UMU will provide the ecosystem for multi-layer computing, especially in the security assurance of the related operations and the dynamic orchestration of network resources. UMU will also exploit RIGOUROUS results in education by strengthening degrees and other high-value training courses, e.g., updating the content of educational courses in line with the technological state-of-the-art. RIGOUROUS will also be exploited by provisioning professional and corporate training services covering leading-edge topics on Security and Privacy. Finally, UMU will also link results with MSc and Ph.D. research works.
ORO	ORO is interested, in principle, in exploiting this project's outcome in prototyping new B2B and B2C products and services based on the technologies and knowledge gained from the current proposal. ORO is interested in building sustainable products, services, and applications aligned with the proposal's objectives and refined by the relevant

	input gathered by OROs Product Management teams from Business Verticals.
LNVO	Lenovo will associate the project with M.Sc./ Ph.D. research and exploit the results for new security and privacy services. The project research specific topics, insights, and deliverables will be contributed to the standardization organization (e.g., such as 3GPP and ETSI work groups) to ensure the standard commercial adoption of the new 6G security services defined by this project RIGOUROUS. Further, it is envisioned that Lenovo commercializes the findings and the created Intellectual Property on the novel concepts and procedures in future products, leveraging the experience in the market and including those within the wide range of the product portfolio where new business opportunities demand security and privacy coupled with AI.
RHEA	RHEA will exploit the security expected RIGOUROUS concept, which initially justifies the cyber resilience of the proposed 6G platform. The central innovative concept of security solution development in RIGOUROUS will be established on two main pillars: 1) Threat Risk Assessment on the proposed 6G platform by tracking and monitoring security risks in the network connectivity and orchestration; 2) Smartly mitigating the identified security risks highlighted in 1). This focus makes RHEA one of the pioneers of cybersecurity solution development in 6G network service providers and operators. RHEA will share the results of the RIGOUROUS within its commercial customer network to demonstrate how RHEA is penetrating the 6G and relative emerging technologies market.
EBOS	As a software powerhouse, EBOS exploitation intentions are geared towards advancing knowledge, cooperation, and collaboration with project partners and stakeholders and reinforcing understanding of improved cyber security through combining AI for threat identification and mitigation actions with the current, state-of-the-art testbed featured at its premises. EBOS will leverage its vast experience in the commercial sector by leading the analysis of the market outlook and the exploitation activities and sustainability plan, ensuring the impact maximization and outreach of the project's results. Through its participation in the project, EBOS expects to advance knowledge and reinforce understanding of its advances, extending the company's R&D activities while expanding EBOS's customer base beyond the current target groups.
WINGS	WINGS will exploit two main results derived from its activities in RIGOUROUS. First, the Cyber-Physical Correlator is already part of the ARTEMIS platform (Artificial Intelligence and IoT Powered Platform for the Proactive Management of Utilities). This component and ARTEMIS service offers: 1) Real-time anomaly detection of utility grid and health monitoring data; 2) Anomaly detection in utility grid SCADA, IT, and IoT Systems data flows; 3) ML approach for intrusion patterns recognition; 4) Implementation of ICT mitigation measures, based on root cause analysis. ARTEMIS is a commercial product, already installed and operated at the national level by Greek utilities. Enforcing the security, privacy, and trust aspects of ARTEMIS will offer our customers an enhanced service and a more competitive solution, potentially increasing our share in the national (and European and international) market. Second, the Dynamic and

	<p>Automated Service Composition will enable WINGS to easily compose services and instantiate custom AI/ML pipelines, as AI-as-a-service, especially for dynamic systems (e.g., IoT/Edge) at the core of the WINGS portfolio of solutions. These systems are expected to scale up and face unknown situations and should be extensible to support new components without re-engineering those currently deployed. The Dynamic and Automated Service Composition will enable not only to offer added value products and services but also to lower CAPEX and OPEX costs for WINGS by facilitating any integration activities.</p>
ONE	<p>In line with the company's business approach, participation in the project will allow ONE to advance its knowledge in security-related topics and pass that knowledge to its core business. ONE plans to enhance its service offering portfolio by incorporating some of the security and AI-related concepts investigated in the project, including the advanced AI-driven anomaly detection mechanisms in its portfolio. Moreover, ONE will leverage the knowledge from the concepts explored in the project to drive new business opportunities in the security domain and AR and VR areas.</p>
ICT-FI	<p>ICT-FI participation in this project will allow strengthening its scientific and technical expertise in cutting-edge research topics, and that is for the benefit of its clients, particularly in the context of securing access to its digital twinning platform as well as securing communications among the platform's micro-services deployed at the extreme edge (gateways), edge cloud and centralized cloud. This vision will be implemented through the following actions: i) incorporating the project results into the knowledge base of the company's staff; ii) using the outcomes of the project to reinforce current R&D initiatives and to strengthen the solution portfolio of the company; iii) exploiting the project results as a catalyst for generating further research projects in relevant scientific and technological areas. The interaction with industrial partners will keep ICT-FI competitive for future research and innovation activities. Exploiting the project's outcomes will enable ICT-FI to develop new business models and enhance its reputation and competitiveness in digital city twinning. ICT-FI is also interested in strengthening its ties within the Consortium and the relevant technological sectors, fostering future collaborations with top-level academic and industrial partners.</p>
OULU	<p>OULU's participation in this project will strengthen its research and technical expertise in future networks and security areas. OULU is also interested in strengthening its ties within the Consortium and the relevant technological sectors, fostering future collaborations with top-level academic and industrial partners. As an academic institution, OULU aims to enrich its teaching activities at different levels (i.e., Bachelor, Master, Ph.D., life-long-learning) concerning vertical industries. This objective will be implemented through two complementary strategies: i) channel the technological knowledge of the project to the teaching program and expose students to real-world problems tackled by the project; ii) incorporate the students in the project and allow them to carry out timely works to prepare them to the technology sectors. Moreover,</p>

	<p>the project's results will also be used to reinforce the research activities carried out by the university. This path will be implemented through: i) incorporating the project results into the knowledge base of researchers; ii) using the project outcomes to strengthen current research initiatives; iii) exploiting the project results as a catalyst for generating further research projects. Finally, OULU will benefit from the project to further enhance its 5G test network and equip it with additional features that will make it more secure.</p>
UWS	<p>UWS is interested in investigating commercialization opportunities of research outcomes in collaboration with partners. The Research & Enterprise Services department at UWS will facilitate such activities. Furthermore, UWS will seek to explore the experiences or results from this and other related ongoing or future research projects to consolidate the leading position of UWS in knowledge transfer in Scotland. Together with regional, national, or international industrial or SME partners, UWS desires to make a significant societal or economic impact on different levels, in line with the university's development strategies. In addition, UWS plans to utilize cutting-edge R&D outcomes, including new algorithms, protocols, software, tools, demos, platforms, etc., from the trials, especially to enhance the teaching materials/facilities in related modules for UWS students at the honors degree and postgraduate/research levels, thereby improving teaching quality and increasing students' satisfaction.</p>
ITAV	<p>As a research institution with strong ties to academia and the industry and a strong tradition of contributions to the networking and orchestration landscape, participation in the project will perfectly align with ITAV's strategy. ITAV expects to strengthen its expertise in Security and Privacy applied to the cyber-resilience of future telecommunications and orchestration solutions, which will result in highly focused and impactful work at scientific and industrial levels. At the innovation and industrial collaborations level, the work developed in RIGOUROUS will be exploited by enabling ITAV to provide targeted training, consulting, and prototyping for a wide range of industrial partners, with a good alignment to the current state-of-the-art. Also related, ITAV has a strong presence in standardization and industry forums, which it expects to be strengthened while enabling the possibility of further disseminating the RIGOUROUS novel approaches.</p>

5.1. Standardization Bodies and Groups

Leveraging the RIGOUROUS cross-sectorial consortia, the project aims at having a broad impact on the ongoing standardization effort in the field of cloud computing, maximize the impact of the project, and foster its exploitation strategies (ensuring RIGOUROUS outcomes are aligned with relevant standards' directions, in order to ensure their market competitiveness). Building on the

RIGOUROUS partner's experience in European and global standard organizations, the project will ensure that results and findings will reflect in the corresponding impact globally. This will be achieved with direct contributions to existing or emerging standards and by indirectly influencing those SDOs through stakeholder's Fora focused explicitly on such objectives. Table 7 presents the most relevant SDOs and Fora the project intends to influence.

Table 7 Addressed standardization bodies and groups and Stakeholders' Fora

Body/Group/WGs	Possible contributions & involved partners
cPPP ECSO	This PPP on cybersecurity is for industry and academia to define the Strategic Research Agenda. RIGOUROUS will bring different aspects of the solution to be provided in the different WG relevant to the certification of security services and systems for Europe WG1 and WG4 on SRIA (UMU).
ETSI ISG MEC, ISG ZSM, ISG NFV, PDL	ETSI NFV was created to define a framework for virtualized network functions and infrastructure and identify existing standards gaps. RIGOUROUS results can positively impact ETSI NFV ISG regarding overall architecture optimization. ETSI CIM focuses on Context Information Management, adding semantics to cloud databases in smart services. UMU will coordinate RIGOUROUS contributions to this group, participating in coordinating cloud standards in ETSI and updates in specifications. LNVO will promote project results related to distributed ledgers and edge services with contributions to ETSI PDL and ETSI MEC, respectively.
IEEE ComSoc IoT Emerging Technologies Subcommittee	UMU (Antonio Skarmeta) is vice-chair of this committee that aims to facilitate initiatives to enable harmonization and convergence on governance, integration, and security of the IoT. In this respect, one of the most promising and relevant contexts is the IEEE P2413, "Working Group on Architectural Framework for the Internet of Things," where seamless interconnection with cloud elements for processing offloading can significantly contribute. RIGOUROUS will contribute to the P2414 standard toward the definition of the functionalities of the virtualization layer regarding the prediction of the performance of the physical devices and dynamic task allocation among them.
AIOTI Standardization WG	eBOS will aim to contribute to the AIOTI Standardization WG through its task force 5 (WG5), focusing on security. eBOS, through the obtained knowledge from the project, will contribute by providing guidelines on a concrete standard framework & references to enable a secure IoT based on security by design while further providing guidelines on IoT security architecture for trusted IoT devices.
5G-PPP / 6G-IA	eBOS aims to contribute towards the identification of standardization

	and regulatory bodies to align with, e.g., ETSI, 3GPP, IEEE, and other relevant standards bodies, & ITU-R (incl. WPs), and WRC (e.g., ECC PT1). Furthermore, eBOS aims to contribute by proposing topics to be standardized & influence the timing of R&D work programs (e.g., EC WPs). UWS will contribute to the envisioned innovations in the architectural components and principles of E2E Control and Management of Network Slicing and Cognitive Close Control Loops.
3GPP (CT1/SA2/SA3/SA5/SA6)	LNVO aims for joint contributions with involved partners and new study item proposals to drive the standardization in line with the project activities.
ITU 5GML FG	UWS, as a full ITU Member, can take the active role of mediator between the innovations produced by the project and the ITU 5GML focus group by proposing new work items and contributions to the agenda of such group on topics related to Machine Learning applied for 5G/6G Network Management.

6 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACHIEVEMENTS

This section reports the early achievements made in the first six months of the project.

6.1. Communication Activities

6.1.1. Web Communication

The website [1] is publicly available, as reported in D6.1. The developed website serves as a comprehensive platform that provides information regarding the work planning, direct links to all project deliverables, dissemination publications and events, consortium details and contacts, and a dedicated news section. The purpose of this approach is to facilitate simpler and more concise publication on social media accounts, particularly LinkedIn while offering more detailed content on the website's news section.

By focusing on delivering succinct and direct information on social media, we aim to increase engagement with our posts. It is well-known that social media followers tend to prefer easily understandable and concise content. However, for those who are more interested and seek further information, they can visit the website to access more comprehensive details.

To avoid adding tracking cookies that would have to be disclosed with a banner on the website, we have used the Cloudflare CDN statistics to drive our visitor statistics. In these early days, we are already surpassing the monthly visitors' KPI set at 300 monthly visitors for the first year. As shown in Figure 1, we had 635 unique visitors this past month. We attribute the higher initial number of

visitors to the relevance of the topics explored by the project, driving visitors to our website to check on the project.

24 Hours 7 Days 30 Days

31 MAY — 30 JUNE

Unique Visitors

950

Total Requests

14.02k

Percent Cached

27.08%

Figure 1 - Website visitor statistics as sourced from Cloudflare

6.1.2. Social Media Communication

The project has an active participation in different social networks. LinkedIn, as a more professional social network, tends to be the first social network where new project updates are published. Figure 2 depicts the impact of published content in terms of impressions.

Metrics

Impressions ▾

Figure 2 - Impact of published content in LinkedIn in terms of impressions

The data shown in Figure 2 is about the number of impressions during May and June. This period is important because it is when we had the most interactions due to the availability of content to share on LinkedIn. On May 30 and May 31, we had a plenary meeting of RIGOUROUS in Aveiro, which resulted in social content for publishing (as shown in Figure 3).

Figure 3 - LinkedIn post from the plenary meeting in Aveiro (May 30 - May 31)

As the post illustrated in Figure 3 corresponds to the initial publication of work-related content resulting from the discussions during the meeting, Figure 4 depicts its analytics.

Figure 4 - Analytics about the post of the plenary meeting in Aveiro

The number of followers is also increasing. During the first 6 months of the project, the LinkedIn account has 75 followers. Figure 5 depicts the evolution of the number of followers during this first semester.

Figure 5 - Evolution of the number of followers in LinkedIn

A high number of followers is an appropriate way to increase project engagement and to share our work with different targets, such as universities including researchers, professors, students, and industry including engineers, stakeholders, and others. Our base strategy to increase the impact on LinkedIn is to share our plenary meeting photos, our participation in public events such as conferences or workshops, and our collaborations with other entities. However, we also

consider it relevant to have the right followers which means that our main concern during this first semester was to share social media accounts with researchers and professionals highly connected to new network generations to increase our visibility.

During the first half of the year, we have also been sharing some of our LinkedIn content on Twitter. However, our initial focus has been on optimizing impressions and engagement, specifically on LinkedIn. As part of our future plans, we intend to broaden our target audience by establishing a presence on other popular social media platforms such as Instagram and Facebook. Additionally, we aim to increase our visibility on Twitter. Furthermore, we are considering sharing of relevant videos on YouTube.

6.1.3. Talks and Events

UMU presented the project to the scientific community during the Secsoft2023 workshop, attended by a total of 45 participants. This engagement resulted in valuable discussions with other projects in the field, focusing on identifying potential synergies and collaborative opportunities.

6.1.4. Project Brochure

The initial project brochure was created within the first six months of project execution. The brochure that was subsequently published in SNS annual journal 2023 prepared by SNS OPS is presented below:

ABOUT

RIGOUROUS project aspires to identify and address the major cybersecurity, trust and privacy risks threatening the network, devices, computing infrastructure, and next generation of services

Introduces a new holistic and smart service framework leveraging new Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence mechanisms, which can react dynamically to the ever-changing threat surface on all orchestration layers and network functions.

6G SNS

HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022

FOLLOW RIGOUROUS

PROJECT COORDINATOR

Antonio Skarmeta
University of Murcia
skarmeta@um.es

secuRe desIGn
and depLOYment
of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum
computing 6G
Services

Figure 6 - First page of the RIGOROUS brochure

Figure 7 - Second page of the RIGOROUS brochure

6.2. Dissemination Activities

6.2.1. Publication and Technical Dissemination

Some papers were published in high-reputation conferences and journals as described below:

Reference	Type	Paper Title
[2]	Journal	Reinforcement Learning-based Slice Isolation against DDoS Attacks in Beyond 5G Networks

[3]	Conference	A Mathematical Model for Analyzing Honeynets and Their Cyber Deception Techniques
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Since the beginning of the project, we are preparing a selection of academic papers for submission to journals and conferences.

When submitting to a journal, the response time is typically longer compared to that of a conference. However, the impact on the scientific community is more substantial when published in a journal. Additionally, conferences play a crucial role in establishing direct communication with attendees, making it the easiest way to connect with other researchers and professionals who share an interest in our project.

Due to these reasons, our current project phase prioritizes the development of high-impact conference papers and papers intended for high-reputation journals. By pursuing this approach, we aim to maximize the project's visibility and influence within the scientific community.

6.2.2. Bachelor, Master, and Ph.D. Thesis and Internships

Throughout the execution of the RIGOUROUS project, we are proposing and publishing various master's dissertations and Ph.D. thesis, in addition to collaborating on final bachelor projects and internships. We believe that these collaborations not only enhance the potential for producing high-quality work but also contribute significantly to the dissemination of our research.

In the initial six-month phase of the project, two theses were concluded and officially published in June 2023 . Additionally, several other thesis topics have been proposed for future development during the subsequent academic year.

Publication Place	Thesis Title
UMU	Implementation and performance analysis in the application of privacy preservation techniques on cyber intelligence information
UMU	Anonymous credential systems: Identity management using zero-knowledge proofs and their performance in embedded systems

By engaging in these collaborative efforts, we aim to leverage the expertise and diverse perspectives of students and professionals. Furthermore, these collaborations enable us to reach a broader audience and ensure that our findings are shared with the academic and professional communities.

Through the integration of masters' dissertations, Ph.D. thesis, and collaborative projects, the RIGOUROUS project aims to not only produce impactful work but also contributes to knowledge exchange and interdisciplinary cooperation.

6.2.3. Standardization Dissemination

For standardization dissemination, the project teams of RIGOUROUS identified different Standards Developing Organizations which can be potential targets to discuss and disseminate contributions related to the RIGOUROUS efforts. Through the duration of the project the aim of the partners will be to target these organization and actively participate in the SDO groups they are involved in or those aligned to their WP topics. The standardization efforts in the first 6 months of the project are summarized in the Table 8.

Table 8 Standardization Dissemination Efforts

Partners	Standardization Efforts / Participation	SDO	Status	Achievement Status (e.g., Contribution(s) Information)
UMU	Security Architecture for 6G	6G-IA	Ongoing	UMU is cochair of the WG that has regular meeting to coordinate the security results of the different projects
	5G Certification process	ECSO	Ongoing	In collaboration with ENISA there is a working activity within WG1 about the certification process and feedback to the EUCS
	Artificial Intelligence Framework for Network Management	IETF NMRG WG	Ongoing	This activity just started and UMU is discussing with Telefonica, NTT and NICT about a possible draft
	Secure onboarding of Network Applications	ETSI	Ongoing	Possible extension proposal to the existing activities related to the management of the trust in the Network descriptors
LNVO	Zero Trust Adaptations for 5G Advanced and 6G systems	3GPP	Ongoing	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 18 TR 33.894 on, 'Study on applicability of the Zero Trust Security principles in mobile networks

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update of Key Issue #1 (S3-231527) • Update to Key Issue #1 (S3-232018) • Additions to the evaluation of tenet 5 on security posture (S3-232102) • Updates to the evaluation of tenet 6 on access security (S3-232103) • Additions to the evaluation of tenet 6 (S3-233320)
	Distributed Ledgers	ETSI PDL	Ongoing	<p>Following contributions were approved for the ETSI GR PDL-019 titled, 'Decentralized Identity and Trust Management':</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDL(23)000_018 - GR PDL-019 DRAFTING SESSION-12 OUTCOME • PDL(23)000_021 - GR PDL-019 DRAFTING SESSION-13 OUTCOME • PDL(23)000_029 - GR PDL-019 DRAFTING SESSION #14 OUTCOME • PDL(23)014_012 - AFTER EDITHELP DGR/PDL-0019 • PDL(23)000_041 - FINAL DRAFT FOR ISG APPROVAL - DGR/PDL-0019_TRUST_MANAGEMENT v0.0.5 (GR PDL 019) • PDL(23)000_022 - GR PDL-019 WORK ITEM TITLE UPDATE
	Secure onboarding of Applications	3GPP	Ongoing	<p>Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 18 TR 33.892 on, "Study on URSP rules to securely identify applications":</p>

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-221811 A solution for KI#1 - Provide additional authentication information to enhance URSP policy enforcement • S3-221902 Scope for TR 33.892 • S3-222425 Solution on enhancing the URSP rule with certificate fingerprint • S3-222564 Assumption on actors and attacker model • S3-224177 Solution on prevention of URSP rule misuse by a non-genuine application using home network anchor • S3-224180 Draft TR 33.892 • S3-231543 Evaluation Update of Solution #2 • S3-231622 Cover sheet TR 33.892 • S3-231543 Evaluation Update of Solution #2 • S3-231556 Draft TR 33.892
EBOS	Guidelines on a concrete standard framework for secure IoT based	AIOTI Standardization WG 5	On going	Following WG5, Task Force focusing on security of IoT- Provide Guidelines and Procedure for enabling secure IoT.
	Identification of standardization and regulatory bodies, e.g. ETSI, 3GPP, IEEE, ITU-R (Incl.WPs), WRC (e.g.ECC PT1)	5G-PPP	On going	In collaboration with Partners, will provide the AI Security framework and standards of the AI-driven Cognitive Decision, Security Orchestration, and Management for the 5G and Beyond, including 6G.
	IoT security architecture	ETSI	On	Provide the contributions-

	for trusted IoT devices.		going	standards based on the upcoming results on 5G and beyond (including 6G) in terms of data communications-interfaces-interorability of the proposed IoT Network Security Architecture for trusted IoT Devices.
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7 REFERENCES

- [1] <https://rigorous.eu/>
- [2] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'fari, T. Taleb and C. Benzaïd, "Reinforcement Learning-based Slice Isolation against DDoS Attacks in Beyond 5G Networks," in *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, doi: 10.1109/TNSM.2023.3254581.
- [3] Javadpour, Amir, et al. "A Mathematical Model for Analyzing Honeynets and Their Cyber Deception Techniques."